
235. Populations in globular clusters

I HAVE DEVOTED several essays to some of the Gaia-based studies of globular clusters: on their Galactic orbits (essay 30), on Palomar 5 and its tidal tails (essay 109), and on Omega Centauri (essays 40 and 157). In essay 230, I discussed the long-standing (and still open) question of the ‘Oosterhoff dichotomy’, related to the average period of their RR Lyrae stars, and which Gaia has shown is tied to the Milky Way’s formation history.

Here I will look at Gaia’s contributions to another globular cluster puzzle: their multiple stellar populations. In their review of this specific phenomenon, and which I will draw on for some of the background, Milone & Marino (2022) described this as ‘...one of the most puzzling, open issues of stellar astrophysics’.

And in their wider review of globular clusters, Gratton et al. (2019) commented that ‘*The increasing amount of observational data are revealing a complexity that has so far defied the attempts to interpret the whole data set in a simple scenario*’.

UNTIL THE 1990s, globular clusters were believed to have formed from a single burst of star formation. Their early formation epochs ($z \gtrsim 3$) would have preceded most of the Galaxy’s assembly. Observations since then have revealed growing evidence for broad or distinct main sequences, red giant branches, and sub-giant branches (e.g. Anderson, 1997; Grundahl et al., 1998; Lee et al., 1999; Bedin et al., 2004; D’Antona et al., 2005; Piotto et al., 2007; Milone et al., 2008; and many others).

Starting with studies of M4 (Marino et al., 2008; 2011), these different populations are now known to be linked to their different abundances, in particular for the elements resulting from H fusion (C, N, O, Na, Al, and in some cases Mg, Si, and K).

Stars with lower N and Na, and higher C and O, resemble Galactic field stars with similar metallicity, and are referred to as ‘first population’ or ‘first generation’ (and denoted 1P or 1G). Conversely, stars enhanced in N and Na (also He and Al), and depleted in C and O, define one or more subsequent stellar populations, and are referred to collectively as second population (2P or 2G).

UNDERSTANDING THE ORIGIN of these multiple stellar populations has proven a challenge for models of stellar evolution, nucleosynthesis, and star-formation processes at high redshift. A simple scenario might attempt to attribute them to different generations of stars: the first burst of star formation would form stars out of pristine material, with subsequent events building stellar populations from their nucleosynthesis products, which then evolve faster. A challenge here that 2P stars represent the majority of stars in most clusters (Milone et al., 2017; Dondoglio et al., 2022). In such a model, this would imply that the progenitors of today’s globular clusters were substantially more massive, having preferentially lost most of their initial 1P stars into the field.

Others have suggested that they form in a single burst of star formation, with a fraction then polluted by the ejecta of more massive stars of the same generation (Bastian et al., 2013; Gieles et al., 2018). Other explanations have been put forward (Milone & Marino, 2022, §4), attributing the chemical anomalies as arising from ‘hot bottom burning’ in asymptotic giant branch stars; massive stars rotating near break-up; massive interacting binaries; the loss of massive stars due to their sinking into black holes; the role of super-massive stars; or the results of stellar mergers. But their conclusion was that ‘*we do not properly understand the origin of multiple stellar populations in globular clusters*’.

As a comment on the field’s nomenclature, ‘chromosome maps’ are 2-colour diagrams derived from colours which maximise the separation of these populations. And clusters are often described as Type I and Type II, based on the distribution of stars in the chromosome maps, or on star-to-star heavy-element variations.

CLUES AS TO how Gaia might assist come from scenarios which predict that these populations also differ in their initial structural and kinematic properties, specifically that 2P stars may form in a sub-system more spatially concentrated than the 1P system (e.g. D’Ercole et al., 2008; Bekki, 2011; Bekki et al., 2017; Calura et al., 2019; Lacchin et al., 2022; Livernois et al., 2024).

TWO MAIN aspects of the Gaia data are being used to throw further light on these multiple populations. The first is the use of the distances and proper motions to probe the morphology and kinematics of the cluster members. Important in this context, and in contrast to HST, is the quasi-inertial nature of Gaia's proper motion system. Another strength is that Gaia's kinematics extend to the outer cluster regions and beyond, compared with HST-based studies which tend to focus on the central regions where the star density is highest.

Studies are also leveraging Gaia's low-resolution XP (BP/RP) spectra, which were made available in Data Release 3 (June 2022) for the 220 million brightest stars. These allow construction of any desired 'synthetic photometry', subject to it lying within Gaia's optical spectral range (essay 187). This is allowing the definition of optimised colour indices (and chromosome maps) to separate the different populations.

THE CLUSTER NGC 1851 is the well-studied prototype of the less-common Type II systems. It shows large differences in both light- and heavy-element abundances, and has been hypothesised to be the remnant of accreted dwarf galaxies. Cordoni et al. (2023) used the low-resolution XP spectra to construct synthetic photometry in the BVI bands, and thence the pseudo-colour index $C_{BVI} = (B - V) - (V - I)$, which has been shown to be effective in separating the metal-rich 'anomalous' stars from the 'canonical' population.

They also constructed an optimised 'chromosome map', m_{F415} versus $m_{F415} - I$, where their Gaia-based F415²⁵ photometric filter (the notation indicating the filter's central wavelength and width, in nm) effectively separates bright red giant branch stars into canonical and anomalous groups (see figure opposite).

They demonstrated that both the canonical and anomalous populations are found both inside and outside the cluster's tidal radius, out to $3.5r_{\text{tidal}}$, or about 45 arcmin. Nonetheless, the canonical population dominates outside the tidal radius, and it exhibits a more circular on-sky morphology, in contrast to the more elliptical shape of the anomalous population.

The Gaia proper motions also give access to the stellar kinematics. And while dynamical differences in the inner regions may be smoothed by relaxation processes, the outskirts of the cluster, characterised by much longer relaxation times, are more likely to retain evidence for any distinct dynamical evolution. And indeed they found hints of a tangentially anisotropic motion in the outer regions, indicating a preference for stars to escape on radial orbits.

They conclude that the Gaia DR3 low-resolution XP spectra, together with Gaia DR3 astrometry and proper motions, are indeed powerful tools for investigating the multiple populations in globular clusters.

A SIMILAR APPROACH was followed by Mehta et al. (2025). They found that the most-efficient filters to distinguish the distinct stellar populations were F380²⁰⁰ and F430¹⁰⁰, which are sensitive to N and C variations respectively. They were able to identify, for the first time, 1P and 2P stars in the cluster's outermost regions and beyond its tidal radius, the 2P stars being more centrally concentrated. Similar chromosome maps effectively distinguished multiple populations in the outer regions of four other clusters with different metallicities: NGC 3201, NGC 6121, NGC 6752, and NGC 6397. Skipping over some detailed differences in these various clusters, the radial dependencies are consistent with cluster formation scenarios where the 2P stars originate in the central regions.

Jang et al. (2025) and Cordoni et al. (2025) extended this approach to examine the radial distributions for 29 globular clusters, using both Gaia and HST proper motions. They found that the 1P stars transition from isotropy to slight tangential anisotropy towards the outer regions, while the 2P stars become increasingly radially anisotropic beyond the half-light radius. Statistically significant differences in the anisotropy profiles were found for dynamically young and non-relaxed clusters. And clusters with orbits closer to the Galactic centre exhibit larger dynamical differences between 1P and 2P stars than those with larger peri-Galactic radii.

Together, their findings are again consistent with a scenario where 2P stars form in a more centrally concentrated environment, and where the interaction with the Milky Way's tidal field plays a crucial role in the dynamical evolution of both populations.

I HAVE BEEN LEFT with the impression that the combination of Gaia's astrometry, and its far-reaching capabilities in the area of synthetic photometry, has only just started its potential impact on this complex problem in the understanding of globular clusters.